

DELIVERABLE

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Authors:

Vincenzo Grillo (CNR)
Alberto Roncaglia (CNR)
Paolo Rosi (UMR)
Amir Tavabi (FZJ)
PengHan Lu (FZJ)
Stefano Frabboni (UMR)
Giulio Pozzi (FZJ)
Enzo Rotunno (CNR)

Contributors:

Gian Carlo Gazzadi (CNR)
Roberto Balboni (CNR)
Rafal Dunin Borkowski (FZJ)

Reviewers:

Matteo Zanfognini (CNR)
Vittorio Morandi (CNR)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of this task was to report about the development toward electrostatic elements for the realization of an Orbital Angular Momentum sorter. We study in particular the parametric dependence on the fabrication and operation details and see a) if the present solution could produce a working sorter b) which improvements are necessary for the final version of the sorter.

The outcomes of this deliverable are strongly related to the realization of deliverable 2.6 “Manuscript for paper on implementation of new phase elements in TEM” which in turn is propaedeutic to the whole WP4 for material science applications and to D5.4 in WP 5.

Whereas we are still considering a magnetostatic device, as for precedent results (D2.2), the electrostatic is the technique of our choice.

The first chapter describes what we should expect as effect of the different alignment and constructive parameters of sorter 1 and 2. The ideal device, in fact, necessarily differs from the actual realized structures. For example, the device is designed assuming a fixed charge distribution but we can only control the applied voltage to the conductors. While the problem with a fixed charge distribution has a relatively easy semi-analytical solution, the induction between conductors makes the solution so complicated that we had to resort to Finite Element calculations. The different shapes of the tips are therefore discussed as well as the use of lateral conductors to correct for aberrations. Further numerically simulated effects regard the actual positioning of the beam and the sorter1 and finally imperfections of sorter 2.

The second chapter describes experimental results about the phase of sorter 1 and 2 obtained experimentally. In fact, we have directly characterized the phase trough the interferometric method. The details of the phase distribution in both devices are analyzed with respect to the simulation in the previous section and in view of the actual application.

The third chapter shows calculation on how experimental devices with their actual phase would behave in a real sorting configuration. We align numerically the devices with the experimental phases in order to simulate the full sorting behavior and check if the present version of the device would work and with which performance.

The fourth chapter illustrates sketches of ideas for the future device not under production. These projects demonstrate how we plan to further improve the performance of the device.

Finally, we conclude discussing open questions and problems in view of future improvements for the actual introduction inside the TEM.

1 EXPECTED RESULTS AND DETAILED DESIGN

As it is well known from the previous results the sorting effect is produced when two appropriate phase elements (hereafter sorter1 and sorer2) are positioned in two planes related by Fourier transformation.

The ideal phases are:

$$\varphi_1(x, y) = \frac{2\pi a}{\lambda f} \left[y \operatorname{atan}\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) - x \ln\left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2+y^2}}{b}\right) + x \right] \quad (1a)$$

$$\varphi_2(u, v) = -\frac{2\pi ab}{\lambda f} \left[\exp\left(-\frac{u}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{v}{a}\right) \right] \quad (1b)$$

Where a,b are free parameters f is the focal length of the lens between the 2 elements. x,y are the coordinate in the first plane and u,v in the relevant diffraction plane. The parameter λ is the particle wavelength.

We use also the scale free parameters $A = 2\pi \frac{aR}{\lambda f}$ (R being the maximum radius of the sorter) and $B = \frac{b}{R}$.

According to the previous results [1][2] and to the D2.2, the sorter1 elements can be obtained approximately by a single charged needle with a fixed charge density along the wire itself. This approximatively works only for a very long needle: a better version of the sorter1 is obtained with 2 additional needles positioned as in figure and a counter electrode producing the image charges shown below (see also: D2.2 Report about working holographic sorter configuration).

Fig 1. (left) Tip of an ideal sorter 1 (where the tip is assumed infinitely long) and relative curves of constant phase. (right) Optimal configuration of electrodes for the sorter1 with astigmatism correction. The rectangle indicates the region that should be invested by the beam to be analyzed. The bottom red electrode, hereafter called “central”, is the main sorting electrode. The two bottom blue electrodes, Hereafter called “lateral” are needed for the astigmatism. The whole structure is replicated in the violet region, for example through the use of an electrostatic mirror.

This extended configuration allows to remove the residual astigmatism induced by the finite length of the main needle in sorter1.

Fig 2 Field and electrodes configuration for the Sorter2. An alternating series of electrodes should produce the phase as in 1b. Here we show the case of the truncated series with a limited set of electrodes.

As for the Sorter2, we need to build an array of positively and negatively biased electrodes.

1.1 More accurate modeling of sorter 1

The idea of sorter1 with the astigmatism correction given by lateral needle is somehow too simplified.

The analytical model above assumed fixed charge for the needle and the use of a mirror in front of the main needle.

In our case, this configuration is not completely realistic for the following reasons:

- What we do is actually controlling the voltage and not the charge in the electrodes. The actual shape of the electrodes and the induction can considerably modify the charge distribution with respect to the ideal case.
- The large electrode in front of the tip is actually as thick as the tip itself. This implies that we cannot assume it is a perfect charge mirror as in the analytical model above.

To gauge the effects of these deviation from the ideal sorter we decided to use Finite element simulations.

The COMSOL Software uses a realistic description of the MEMS geometry and the therefore account for these effects. It solves the 3D Dirichlet electrostatic problem of the biased conductor including any mutual induction.

Fig 3 geometry of the conductors in the finite elements simulation of the sorter1

The SEM image below represents the actual device. And as it can be seen, the geometry is very similar to the simplified model above except for the continuation of the tip outside the frame.

Fig 4 SEM image of the sorter1 structure with lateral electrodes for astigmatism correction. Additional electrodes circuits on the bottom right are here not used.

The finite elements is a numerical method so normally we lose the predictive value of an analytical calculation. However even before using the numerical methods we were already able to predict an interesting effect in actual devices:

If the tip thickness is uniform the charge will tend to concentrate toward the tip.

If this is true, a simplified toy model would be to assume the charge as a uniform distribution (as in the ideal device) plus a concentrated charge at the tip.

The main effect of such charge is to add a phase superimposed to the sorting potential

$$\varphi = \varphi_0 \ln(|\vec{r} - \vec{r}_0|)$$

This is a sort of logarithmic focusing of the beam before sorting.

1.2 Finite elements and Modelling of the tip

For the tip we used 3 types of geometry that are shown in the figures below.

Briefly, we can describe the tips as parallelepiped (a), elliptical cylinder (b) and ellipsoid (c).

The relevant projected potential for each configuration are shown in fig 5 d,e,f.

Fig 5 Geometry of the electrodes and total phase for sorter1 for different shape of the tip

The results of the calculation were exported as values of the potentials (a 1024 x 1024 x 100 pts grid) written in an ascii text file.

This grid of potential value per each point was then fed into a software that converts the grid of values of the potentials (written in the text file) into an image that is just the 2D map of the sum of the potential along z.

In fact what matters for us is only the phase acquired by the electron in each point that is:

$$\phi(x, y) \propto \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} V(x, y, z) dz$$

that we approximate to an integral in the region of the Finite element calculation extending for about 100 μm above and below the device.

The apparently smooth phase landscape resulting from these simulations is still not appropriate for checking the sorting properties.

In fact, the finite elements calculation intrinsically involves a discontinuity on derivatives. This is due to the simulation scheme that solves, for the electrostatic potential, the laplacian equation of electrostatic separately in each subdomains in which the volume of simulation is divided. It then connects continuously (but with discontinuous derivative) the solution for each domain. This creates a set of jumps in the derivatives every time a border between subdomains is encountered.

Since the sorting is based on diffracting the wave in a position determined by the local gradient of the sorter phase, these discontinuity in the derivative produce an artificial degradation of the solution.

We, therefore, applied a further elaboration of the projected potential map taking advantage of the fact that the phase must be $\nabla_{xy}^2 \phi = 0$ everywhere outside the tips.

Therefore, we applied the following filtering procedure

- Calculate the $\nabla_{xy}^2 \phi$
- Apply a mask, where $\nabla^2 \phi = \rho$ if $|\rho| < \epsilon$ put $\rho = 0$
- Calculate inverse laplacian (through Fourier transforming)

This approach permits to generate smoother, and therefore more realistic, description of the sorting effect with almost no discontinuity in the derivatives.

Assuming now that the 3 phase landscape shown in fig 5 are correctly calculated we need to study which one is more similar to the theoretical image.

For the sake of comparison, below we plotted the theoretical case of $A=5$ $B=1.5$. These parameters have been selected by visual inspection to be more close to the set of parameters reachable by the electrostatic device.

Fig 6 Phase of an ideal sorter.

We can note both the similarities and differences between the realistic phase landscapes calculated by finite elements in fig 5 and the ideal sorter1 phase in fig 6.

Depending on the parameters there are indeed a round tip and straight lateral parts. The straight lateral parts are visible in all 3 configurations in fig 3 so it is difficult to understand which one is preferable.

In order to understand this differences, we must analyze the diffraction

Preliminarily we calculated the diffraction from a theoretical sorter at different values of the parameter a or its reduced form A .

Fig 7 Diffraction for an ideal sorter 1 and a petal beam ($L=\pm 5$) with increasing value of the parameter $A=1, 5, 30$.

Varying this simulation parameter corresponds roughly, in experiments, to vary the voltage of the tip.

The simulations in fig 7 are obtained for a petal beam obtained by the superposition of 2 vortex beams of topological charge ± 5 . The ideal sorter should produce perfectly alternating lines of intensity.

The simulations indicate that the best transformation of coordinates is obtained for larger values of A . This was already predictable since the condition of work for the sorter is within the stationary phase approximation that implies that the phase in the sorter must be stronger than the beam's phase. In experimental terms this implies that the voltage of the central tip must be increased and this, in turn, implies that, when all other lenses are unchanged we obtain a larger magnification of the diffraction of sorter1 .

Now the actual size of the sorter1 diffraction is bound to fit to the size of sorter 2 period.

Since the size of sorter2 is fixed by the geometry the increase of the parameter A must be compensated by a different excitation of the lenses, in particular a smaller focal length of the overall lens system. This must be well kept in mind during the experiment,

Fig 8 Diffraction of a petal beam ($L=+/-5$) impinging on 3 different sorter1 tip: rectangular (a) , elliptic cylinder (b), ellipsoid (c).

For the simulation we just need to multiply the phase by a large scale factor. We therefore used a relatively large factor to test the effects of the different tips.

The figure shows the effect of the different tip shape on the sorter1 diffraction when a petal beam ($L=+/-5$) is superimposed to the sorter.

The tips produce a different form of bending of the diffraction. Apparently the ellipsoid that is the most correct shape, produces the most straight line.

As anticipated the interpretation would be that the logarithmic focusing term due to charge accumulation on the tip produces a sort of artificial focusing.

Of course the tapering of the electrodes in the ellipsoid electrodes seem to act as a better counter-balance of this charge accumulation.

However we will see in a moment that a similar effect is produced also by a slight misalignment of the tip w.r.t. the beam. So we cannot exclude that a slight variation of the position could cause these differences.

1.3 The effect of position

Fig 9 Different positioning of sorter1 with respect to the a petal beam and their effect on the sorter1 diffraction. In a, b the electrode tip is aligned to the center of the beam. In c,d the beam has been shifted with respect to the sorter to obtain optimal nearly straight diffraction.

Another effect that should be accounted for is the exact positioning of the tip and the beam.

In experiments we are not indeed able to align the reciprocal position with extreme precision. However even if we were able we need to know what exact alignment we should aim for. We will see that the intuitive condition with the tip exactly in the center of the beam is not necessarily the most correct.

For this reason we used a function of STEMCELL software that permits to move the relative position of the tip and the beam while looking at the Fourier transform. We identified in fig 9 two possible conditions. One is the most intuitive case when the tip terminates at the exact center of the petal beam and is depicted in fig 9 a,b. Whereas the lobes are well visible the diffraction is clearly bent in an arch something that simulations with the ideal sorter do not indicate as standard sorting condition.

Fig 9 c,d instead describe the situation where we moved the tip until we find a straight diffraction. We find that this condition corresponds to advancing the tip in the beam. It also results in a more irregular diffraction intensity.

The explanation can be found in a simple consideration: in the ideal sorter a line of phase singularity (there the phase gradient is discontinuous) is clearly visible (see also fig 6). Physically this line of singularity is reproduced by a constant line of charges and the perfect sorting is obtained when the extremity of this line is in the center of the beam.

However a conductor does not have fixed charge distribution but fixed potential surface: the tip geometry should not correspond to the line of charges but to an equipotential line surrounding the ideal line of charge distribution.

Fig 10 Line of constant charge (red) and line of constant potential (yellow) for an ideal sorter.

This concept is illustrated in figure 10 where we can see that to a line of constant charge (in red) corresponds an ellipsoidal equipotential surface (in yellow) that should be therefore corresponds to the shape of the electrode. Notice that the line of charge can be also substituted by a thick surface in the z direction (since what matters is only the z projection). In such case we could just think of this as the superposition of the field of many lines of charge. This solution must be recalculated but it cannot be very different from the qualitative result in fig 11.

Fig 11 Surface of constant potential for an ideal sorter with a thick surface of charge along z

1.4 The effect of lateral tips

Fig 12 Sorter1 diffraction for a central voltage if $V_c=20V$ and lateral electrode voltages of $V_L=-10, 0, 10V$

If we now take into account all the above effects we are ready to consider the effect of the lateral electrodes on the sorting. In fact while we can predict the effect of these tips for the case of fixed charge, the use of the actual fixed potential condition is more complicated. The induction between different conductors could, indeed, lead to a different solution for the overall phase.

Fig 12 is done putting a tension of $V_c=20$ V on the central electrode, and the 2 lateral counter electrodes at the same voltage V_L .

The geometry selected for this test is the one with a rectangular central electrode and the nominal best value for $V_L \approx 0.5V_C$ so in this case $V_L = -10$ as in fig 12a. However when the voltage is changed to 0 and positive the overall shape of the diffraction remains similar except for a small scale factor. In fact the use of a different potential V_L changes the effective reference ground. This effect is large because the lateral tips are as thick as the final grounded mirror

It is difficult from this image alone to judge if the difference in the phase distribution can be accommodated by a simple scale factor.

1.5 Sorter 2

For the sorter 2 the problems are much less complicated than for sorter 1 since the details of the electrodes should not really affect the final result. In principle no part of the beam should touch the electrodes, The details of the electrode become rigorously negligible only if the beam is sufficiently far from the electrodes. On the other hand if the number of electrodes is limited we are forced to reconsider the distance over which the sorter 2 works correctly. A rule of thumb solution is to assume that the field is correct in the central line region up to a maximum distance of the order of $D/2$ where D is the lateral extension of the line of electrodes.

The present version of the sorter 2 features only 7 contacts that are therefore just sufficient to produce a correct phase region in proximity of the electrodes. This means that the field at the extremes of the electrodes become very relevant. This will change in future version of sorter 2 with more electrodes.

Therefore, we need to care for the details of the electrodes. As anticipated in the previous release of the deliverable we need to polish by FIB the shape of the electrodes in order to produce a perfectly shaped sorter2.

In particular we noticed that the MEMS fabrication produced a typical enlargement of the electrodes toward its basis. In the previous version of the deliverable this has been mistaken for a contamination effect that still is present. For the next version of the sorter2 as a further caution we also increased the separation of the electrodes.

The cleaning process is here described for a 6 and 7 electrodes version of sorter2.

Fig 13 SEM image of the sorter 2 device with 7 electrodes.

Fig 14 Example of FIB polishing of sorter 2 with 6 and 7 contacts. The image show on left the original structure and on the right the structure after polishing.

Fig 15 shows a numerical simulation based on finite elements that confirms the qualitative consideration above: only a small region indicated by a rectangle is useful as a sorter 2. The slight left-right asymmetries are numerical errors but the overall difference to the ideal sorter 2 are quite evident in the peripheral regions.

Fig 15 (a) Finite elements simulation of the phase of sorter 2 with 7 electrodes. The region of interest for matching with sorter1 diffraction is also indicated by a red rectangle. For comparison in fig (b) a calculation for an ideal sorter2 is also shown.

2 EXPERIMENTAL HOLOGRAPHY OF THE DEVICES

We present here the experimental data regarding the new sorter devices. The phases do look quite similar to what expected but there are interesting differences. The most important

regards the shape of the tip. It is very irregular and asymmetric. As we discussed in the previous section the shape of the tip is crucial in the definition of the field.

Fig 16 Holographic reconstruction of the phase for $V_C=1V$ and $V_L=0$ (a) , $0.5V$ (b) , $1V$ (c). The optimal voltage is show in b and is more similar indeed to the ideal case in fig 1a.

The image a and c also present a very early closure of the field line that indicate probably an accumulation of charge in the tip region due to its shape. This charge accumulation exceeds even the computation for a parallelepiped electrode and we can make the hypothesis that due to the imperfect conductivity of the wire and the electron beam irradiation the voltage is not uniform along the wire. However images done with opposite voltage applied to the tip produce very symmetric results and this seems to rule out the charging due to the beam. An enlargement of image of the field about the tip is also shown in the figure below

Fig 17 Zoom of the experimental phase of sorter 1 revealing the effect in proximity of the tip. A certain asymmetry can be noticed

The figure below is an image of the sorter 2 with 7 contacts . The holography shows that the region with the correct phase is quite limited. In general a bit of fine tuning of the voltages has been necessary in order to obtain the correct phase at least in the indicated region.

Fig 18 Comparison of the experimental (left) and simulated (right) phase of sorter2. The main voltage of the alternate electrodes was $\pm 2V$.

3 FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERIZATION

Here we characterized the work of the sorter1 electrodes in a qualitative way. Using out of focus condition of nominally 10 mm we were able to verify the effect of a variable voltage of the central and lateral electrodes. The use of out of focus condition is necessary in order to transform the phase effect into an amplitude effect directly observable.

Fig 19 Experimental “out-of focus” image of the 3 tips of the sorter 1 . The lateral tips are help to a voltage equal to zero while the central tip voltage is varied.

The image clarity show caustic that become dark (with positive voltage) or bright (with negative voltage) .

In the first series of image above we can notice that the applied voltage on the central wire influences the image of the lateral wire. This is even more impressive if we notice that at $V_c=20$ the contrast of the lateral electrodes passes from black to white.

Fig 20 Experimental “out-of focus” image of the 3 tips of the sorter 1 . The central tips is set to a fixed voltage while the lateral tip voltage are varied together.

The effects of the induction can be also found by inspection of fig 20. The increase of the voltage of the lateral tips induces a slight enlargement of the shadow of the central tip and a strong deformation of the shadow of the mirror electrode in front of the central tip.

3.1 Diffraction and sorting properties

The most important feature of the sorter1 must be to produce a correct diffraction. In particular the phase must match that of the phase corrector. The amplitude is readably

visible in the diffraction of the object but for the phase we need to do a more advanced characterization.

For this reason we acquired images at different diffraction defoci and extracted the phase through the method of Transport of Intensity Equation to the diffracted beam [3].

The result is shown below. Since the foci are not well known the phase was calculated apart for a multiplicative scale factor. This turns out to be not a big problem since the sorter itself is defined apart for a scale factor a .

As a further test we also calculate the Fourier transform finding the wavefunction at the sorter plane. This confirms the quality of the phase reconstruction.

Fig 21 Intensity and phase (in colorscale) of the diffraction of sorter 1 as obtained through transport of intensity equation. The correspondence between colors and phase is illustrated in the inset.

Fig 22 (a) Fourier transform of the diffracted wavefunction: this permits to reconstruct the wave at the sorter 1 plane and is used as a cross check with the experiment to test the quality of the reconstruction. The actual wave at the sorter 1 plane is shown in fig b.

The most important test has been however to stack all elements and predict the performance of the whole sorter.

For this reason we made sure that the diffraction of sorter1 matched in size the active area of sorter2. Using then the alignment algorithm of STEMCELL described in previous section we were able to find the most concentrate diffraction. This condition is what is also used in real experiment where the two elements are aligned by checking the actual OAM spectrum.

Mathematically the operation of alignment can be written as

$$\Psi(x,y) = IFT(FT(S1(x,y) \cdot P(x,y)) \cdot T_{\Delta u, \Delta v}(S2(u,v)))$$

P is the probe to be sorted (in this case just a constant) FT and IFT represent the direct and inverse Fourier Transform , T the translation operation necessary for alignment and the factors $S1(x,y) = \exp(i\phi_1(x,y))$

$$S2(u,v) = \exp(i\phi_2(u,v))$$

represent the effect of the sorter phase elements.

Fig 23 shows indeed (a) sorter 1 diffraction calculated from experimental data, (b) the sorter2 experimental phase (c) the resulting phase after the alignment (d) the final spectrum . Since there was no structure in the original beam the spectrum peak should correspond to the OAM=0 condition. Unfortunately we can see in fig c that the phase is still not completely stationary. This is an indication that some part of the sorter is not perfectly aligned possibly due to imperfections of the time.

Fig 23 Simulated sorting experiment using experimental phases of sorter 1 & 2 . The diffraction of sorter1 (a) is superimposed to sorter2(b) and after the alignment the wave in(c) is diffracted to a single line (d).

Fig 24 Simulation of alignment procedure based on OAM spectrum inspection and based on experimental phases of sorter1 &2: varying the relative position of the sorter1 and 2 we can obtain a very localized peak in the ideal case. In this case the peak is still quite narrow.

The series of figure 24 shows the alignment procedure that slowly brings from an image of the beam in the sorter plane to the OAM spectrum through a successive alignment that aims at the smaller OAM spectrum.

In order to test the resolution of the full sorter configuration we also used a petal beam ($L=\pm 5$) and the experimental phase as above trying to obtain by iterative alignment the best resolution.

The results are shown below. The alignment, orientation and magnification are done visually as in experiments and we find that the spectrum still allows for a very good separation of the peaks at $L=\pm 5$. This also permits to calculate the OAM standard deviation as $0.96 \hbar$

Fig 25 Simulated spectrum with experimental phases for a petal beam $L=\pm 5$.

The spectral lines are not perfectly straight and the peaks side-lobes are among the most evident defects. Still we clearly see that even in very inaccurate conditions the sorter can work to an almost satisfactory level.

4. FUTURE STRUCTURES

In order to improve the sorter we work in particular on the tip shape. We used FIB to produce round shaped tips that resembles more the ideal ellipsoid whereas still elongated.

Fig 26 Sorter 1 after the changes introduced by FIB

We also worked on removing the electrostatic mirror in sorter 1 and to substitute it with an explicit copy of the tip opposite to the main tip itself.

Fig 27 project of the new MEMS structures with an explicit mirror of the needle structure. The mirror plane, here dashed, corresponds to the position of the previously grounded electrode.

We are also adding the possibility to add a simple heating electrode to make a sort of bake and remove contaminants from the tip.

Fig 28 Sorter 1 structure with a heater attached to the main central tip

Finally we are modifying the sorter 2 in order to make 11 contacts using 8 contacts and maintaining the planar geometry .

Fig 29 Sorter 2 with 11 contacts. The 11 contacts are still obtained in planar configuration.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND OPEN PROBLEMS

Overall the simulations and experiments so far bring mainly a positive result: in spite of the apparently coarse alignment and phase definition it is possible to “easily” arrive to an electrostatic sorter that works with a resolution of 1h . This is at least comparable with the resolution of the holographic sorter so far published [4].

In spite of this general impression we expect that a large improvement is obtained with the following improvements: 1) better shape of the tip in terms of symmetry, roundness and approximation to an ellipsoid 2) improved alignment of the sorters in terms of rotation, translation, magnification. 3) increased number of electrodes in sorter 2 in order to make the phase more similar to the ideal case. 4) better understanding of the role of the lateral electrodes as astigmatism corrector or use of a longer tip in order to reduce in any case the imperfection of the electric fields.

References

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ANNEX 1: REFEREE COMMENTS

Referee 1 Vittorio Morandi

First of all I would like to express my appreciation for the large amount of work that has been done in this deliverable. I think the text is quite clear and the physics is very interesting.

I am in particular impressed of the predictive character of the Finite Element simulations coupled with STEMCELL. I think that the complete series of simulations from the field to the sorting permits to optimize the actual experiment.

In this regard I am wondering if it would be possible to study also the caustic obtained in fig 19 and 20?

Yes as an example consider in the figure below the simulation that matches the experimental data for $V_c=20V$ $V_L=-10V$. However we decided it is not necessary to get into deep details of this simulation. The experimental data already gives a nice idea of the fact that the circuit is correctly working and that there is an induction effect between the electrodes.

The fig 9 shows still a quite fuzzy contrast, what is the reason?

In spite of the filtering procedure imposing $\nabla_{xy}^2 \varphi = 0$ the phase can still contain discontinuity that affect the diffraction.

In fig 23a there is an additional bright dot below the main diffraction. What is its origin and why it does not appear in the actual diffraction such as fig 21?

The dot is an artifact due to the fact that we are assuming the tip of the sorter1 as a pure phase object, neglecting the fact that it is actually completely absorptive.

Referee 2. Matteo Zanfrognini

In this deliverable both theoretical and experimental advances in the design and fabrication of electrostatic orbital angular momentum sorters are reported also suggesting possible new solutions to improve the performances of these devices and to simplify their use in real life electron microscopy experiments. The experimental characterization performed on these devices underlines the possibility of having a resolution in OAM of about $1\hbar$, comparable with the one which can be obtained through holographic sorters.

Comments:

I think Figure 1 should contain a clearer identification of the elements forming the Sorter1 (the two needles and the counter electrode) together with a comment to each of the pictures forming Figure 1.

We thank the referee for this comment. The information were already contained in the deliverable 2.2 but for clarity we reported everything in detail in the caption of fig 1

I think it could be useful to clarify the effect of charge concentration at the tip in Section 1.1: in particular the reason for which such a charge induce focusing before sorting.

This can be answered by noticing that the phase from a point charge obeys a 2D laplacian problem equivalent to

$$\nabla^2 \varphi = a\delta(\rho - \rho_0)$$

That produces the logarithmic solution. Since realistically the charge is not accumulated in a single point there can be small deviation from this.

It could be useful to add some details about the relative position of the tip and of the beam in the caption of Fig.9, in particular quantifying the distance among the tip and the center of the petal beam in b) and d), similarly to what explained in the main text.

Done

Is it possible to explain the reason why the calculations presented in Sec. 1.4 and shown in Fig. 12 have been performed assuming a rectangular central electrode?

A rectangular central electrode is what can be easily fabricated with MEMS technology. We have improved this by using FIB.

At the same I cannot understand why the nominal best value for the potential applied to the lateral electrodes is half the one on the central one.

This has been calculated empirically in the deliverable D2.2 and may change for a different geometry.

I think a brief justification about why working in out of focus condition of 10 mm could be a good approach for a functional characterization of the Sorter1 could be inserted at the beginning of Chapter 3.

We added the following sentence

“The use of out of focus condition is necessary in order to transform the phase effect into an amplitude effect directly observable.”

In my opinion, a short description of the results obtained fixing the central electrode potential while varying the voltage applied on the lateral ones should be added in the same chapter.

The effects of the induction can be also found by inspection of fig 20. The increase of the voltage of the lateral tips induces a slight enlargement of the shadow of the central tip and a strong deformation of the shadow of the mirror electrode in front of the central tip.

In Fig. 22 it is necessary to indicate which of the figures is the Fourier transform of the diffracted wave and which is the function at the Sorter1 plane.

We added a and b label

In Chapter 3 “DIFFRACTION AND SORTING PROPERTIES” the Figure 23 c) is commented saying that the phase is not completely stationary.

There is indeed in fig c a small phase gradient that should not be there for a perfectly $L=0$ beam.

Furtherly the mathematical description of the alignment procedure should be introduced at the beginning of this chapter as it clarifies in a deep way this particular procedure, up to here described only qualitatively.

We shifted the equation and relevant description few lines above.

I think it could be useful to insert a few more information about the way in which the images presented in Fig. 24 have been obtained. More clearly, which is, for example, the degree of dis-alignment between Sorter1 and Sorter2 in the second image on the left in Fig. 24 ?

Thanks for the question but it is even difficult to represent this graphically. The figure below indicates with a rectangle the two corresponding regions when the diffraction is like in fig 24a

In Fig.25 the expected OAM spectrum for a ± 5 petal beam is evaluated starting from the experimentally measured phases of Sorter1 and Sorter2, showing a good resolution in OAM. I wonder if there is a reason for which the peak for $L = +5$ is more intense than the one for L

= -5 (an unbalance of about 10 % is observed), while they should have the same intensity. In particular I cannot understand which non-ideality of the presented sorting apparatus is effectively responsible of this spurious asymmetry.

This is a very serious problem when we will have to afford EMCD for example. Most probably this is caused by the asymmetry of the sorter1 tip as explicitly mentioned in fig 17.

Notice also that there is a side lobe of the peak at $L=-5 \hbar$ that could account for the loss of intensity. For the actual experiment a calibration of the response of the sorter should be carried on before the actual application.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Multi Modal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL